

Critical Making

DI.I PROJECT HANDBOOK

**Incl. QA plan and ethical requirements
according to EC regulations**

image cc by Careables Consortium

DOCUMENT DATA

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering EV, Germany
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
CMAB	Critical Making Advisory Board
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
PMB	Project Management Board
PU	Public
RE	Restricted
RIA	Research & Innovation Action
R&I	Research & Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
STEM	Science Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
SwafS	Science with and for Society

TUB Technische Universität Berlin, Germany

VTT Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY, Finland

WIF Wikifactory Europe SL, Spain

WP Work Package

WP1 Project Management

WP2 Building the critical making knowledge-base: concept & methods

WP3 Case Action: GENDER

WP4 Case Action: YOUNG TALENTS

WP5 Case Action: OPENNESS

WP6 Evaluation, Impact, Future Implications

WP7 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

ZSI Zentrum für Soziale Innovation, Austria

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Project Handbook describes the internal procedures of the Critical Making consortium in terms of management structures, communication and collaboration as well as quality control measures. It also defines the way Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) practices are integrated into our own project work, especially considering ethical issues related to personal data collection, analysis and storage. This will be elaborated then in more detail in the Data Management Plan. Open source and open access are important elements of RRI and the strategy of the consortium in dealing with these aspects is also reflected in this document.

The main target group for this deliverable is the consortium partners themselves as this handbook defines the project's internal processes for securing high quality research work to be performed across a set of complementary partner institutions. It serves as a reference document for all Critical Making team members including individuals joining in the project at a later stage.

Since the project is bringing together a set of diverse experts from different fields and backgrounds, a core principle guiding internal processes is open participation and flexibility. Transparency about the project status as well as risk recognition are additional principles that the project partners are committed to.

Still, in order to effectively operate in a small, but distributed team, we have defined some procedures of how to best communicate and structure our collaboration. Regular meetings are held via videoconference as well as face-to-face. Communication is also taking place via a Signal group, e-mail and the project mailing list. The main tool for sharing and collaborating on documents is Nextcloud.

The consortium is committed to producing high quality research outcomes and deliverables and thus quality control is important. Quality guidelines describe the internal peer review process, which is applied to all project deliverables. In order to continuously improve our internal processes, regular internal reflections are performed, normally in the context of project meetings. These reflections on the collaboration are intended for the whole group to serve as a self-reflection and self-evaluation tool about the project structures.

In terms of ethics, the consortium is following the general rules defined by the EC and commits strongly to respect the individual and their privacy at all times. Templates have been prepared for informed consent as well as the exchange of primary research data

amongst partners that may contain personal data from study participants. The document also considers personal data collection, processing and storage to be in line with the GDPR.

Finally, openness is a core value of the project and thus the consortium is looking into open strategies with regards to the research outcomes. This relates to hardware that may be published under specific open licenses, following and where possible contributing to open standards, as well as the research publications, which should be made openly accessible as far as possible.

This handbook is understood as a living document and is updated if the need arises in order to improve the internal processes.

INTRODUCTION

The Critical Making project is committed to high quality output and responsible research and innovation. Thus, this document defines a set of procedures that the consortium is committed to adhering to and improving in the course of the project.

Openness and transparency are two of the guiding principles that the reader will see reflected in the different processes and methods described. At the same time, there is a strong awareness within the consortium related to privacy and data protection of individual participants. These core principles underlying the research work in Critical Making correspond with the practices related to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI).

Section 2 below describes the management structures, including the nominees for the various boards. Section 3 is dedicated to specific quality management procedures, including communication structures and tools, the peer reviewing process for high quality deliverables as well as risk management, and other quality assurance means. In Section 4 the technical infrastructure for communication and collaboration is presented. Section 5 presents the RRI policies and identifies the most relevant aspects for Critical Making. It includes the ethical approach and guidelines that the project is following. In Section 6 the consortium's strategy towards openness is described and relates to open source in terms of software as well as open access in terms of publications and other project results. Finally, Section 7 draws the conclusions that are relevant for high quality implementation of the project.

The appendix includes examples of templates mentioned throughout the document, such as the Informed Consent.

MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE

Both the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA) specify the number of bodies for the management of the project. Though the GA and CA, being legal documents, take precedence over this handbook, the following sections specify the operational view of these bodies.

Critical Making is a research and innovation action (RIA) formed by a small number of consortium partners. Therefore, the management structure and procedures work in a flexible manner in order to:

- Achieve integration of all consortium members and mobilise their expertise, knowledge and networks in every stage of the project
- Efficiently coordinate the processing of the work plan in a collaborative environment
- Continuously involve contextual expertise and knowledge of relevant stakeholders (e.g. makers, practitioners, researchers, educators) and their networks

Our approach is a combination of integration and decentralisation strategies. Integration is achieved through the composition of a consortium with complementary skills and knowledge, the development of a joint framework, the agreement on common guidelines for co-design activities, sharing of common cases across the different topics, and project workshops and meetings. The resources of all partners will be mobilised by decentralisation of responsibilities through the assignment of leadership for work packages and defined work package tasks with a clear task sharing based on the different competence fields of the partners.

Figure 1: Critical Making – Management Structure: responsible roles in management

The management structure defines the basic roles and responsibilities. The Coordinator (Dr. Barbara Kieslinger, ZSI) is responsible for the overall line of actions and the day-to-

day management carried out by the project. Additional ZSI staff is providing financial and administrative support to the coordinator.

The Project Coordinator is supported by the Project Management Board that manages the project on an operational and strategic level.

WORK PACKAGE (WP)

The work package (WP) is the building block of the project. The WP leader organises the WP and coordinates the different tasks, prepares and chairs WP meetings, organises the production of the results of the WP, represents the WP in the Project Management Board.

Each work package has been appointed a Work Package Leader who is responsible for the progress within the work package and who is supported by task leaders and other members of the consortium involved in each of the WPs. Clear responsibilities (based on the competencies of each partner) are described in the Work Package Description. Current WP leaders are shown in Table I.

Workpackage	Lead partner	Name
WP1 Project Management	ZSI	Barbara Kieslinger
WP2 Building the Critical Making knowledge-base: concept & methods	TUB	Regina Sipos
WP3 Caes Action: GENDER	ZSI	Teresa Schäfer, Lisa M. Seebacher
WP4 Case Action: YOUNG TALENTS	TUB	Melanie Stilz
WP5 Case Action: OPENNESS	GIG	Sandra Mamitzsch
WP6 Evaluation, Impact, Future Implications	VTT	Maria Akerman
WP7 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication	WIF	Carolina Portugal

Table I Current WP leaders

PROJECT MANAGEMENT BOARD (PMB)

The project is managed through the Project Management Board (PMB). It provides the overall direction for the project, both strategic and operational. The PMB maintains the project directions and obtains advice from the Work Package Leaders, to ensure that the project meets its stated and implied goals. The PMB ultimately supervises all project management processes, including initiation, planning, execution, control, and closure of project phases. Within this framework, the Work Package Leaders coordinate the detailed planning, execution and control of the technical tasks to meet the project's scientific and technical objectives relevant to their work packages.

The PBM is also responsible for overseeing the project's scientific work from a strategic level. This includes the following duties and responsibilities: to organise the scientific meetings, to check that decisions made at these meetings are carried out, to circulate minutes, reports and papers to all relevant project participants, incl. the Advisory Board. The PBM will also be responsible for the ongoing development and refinement of the overall project vision.

The PMB is chaired by the Project Coordinator and composed of one delegate (the Partner Leader) from each Partner. Each Partner shall have one vote and shall clearly identify their delegate with the right to vote to the project coordinator. The PMB shall not deliberate and decide validly unless a majority of 75% of its members are present or represented.

The PMB meets at least twice a year, either physically or virtually and on a specific request of one of the work package leaders or a project partner.

Only the PMB has the authority to

- Accept or reject changes to the work plan, thus it takes all decisions regarding the Grant Agreement and amendments to the Consortium Agreement,
- Send proposals to the EC,
- Make changes in the Project Management structure

In the case of a vote, each party shall have one vote. Decisions are reached by a majority of two-thirds of the voters present or represented at a meeting. In the case a party cannot agree with a decision taken by the PMB, he/she can veto and resubmit an action to the PMB. In this case, a 75 % majority of all partners present or represented in the PMB is needed for a final decision.

The PMB is currently composed of the persons listed in Table 2 below.

Partner	Partner manager
ZSI	Barbara Kieslinger
TUB	Regina Sipos
VTT	Maria Akerman
WIF	Carolina Portugal
GIG	Sandra Mamitzsch

Table 2: Partner managers

CRITICAL MAKING ADVISORY BOARD

The Critical Making Advisory Board (CMAB) is a group of persons from outside the project. The CMAB will be consulted for important decisions that affect the direction of research and/or are related to the adoption of the results from the Critical Making project according to the CA and the GA.

The CMAB members are listed in Table 3.

CMAB member	Affiliation
Ingeborg Meijer	University of Leiden, Netherlands
Niels Meijlgaard	Aarhus University, Denmark
Maximilian Voigt	German Association of Makerspaces, Germany
Emad Yaghmaei	TU Delft, Netherlands
Stephanie Wuschitz	Mz Baltazar's Laboratory, Vienna, Austria
Hannah Perner-Wilson	University of Performing Arts Ernst Busch, Berlin, Germany
Alessandra Schmidt	Make Works, IAAC Fablab Barcelona, Spain
Thomas Hervé Mboa Nkoudou	Open Bioeconomy Lab, Cameroon

Table 3: CMAB members

During the Kick-off meeting, it was decided that this group of external experts can still be expanded with 2-3 persons for strategic purposes.

CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT (CA)

Before the start of the project, a consortium agreement has been signed by all partners. It defines the specific operational procedures for the different project bodies described above. This includes, amongst other aspects, the responsibilities of the parties and their liabilities towards each other as well as the governance structure, financial provision and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues. The consortium agreement also describes the decision-making structures and defines the General Assembly as the ultimate decision-making body.

QUALITY PROCEDURES AND CODE OF CONDUCT

Quality assurance is of high priority in collaborative research, such as Critical Making, and the consortium is committed to a set of quality procedures to guarantee high quality project output. Measures to ensure good quality include e.g. the definition of internal communication structures, regular internal reflections on risks as well as a defined peer review process for any project deliverable. The detailed procedures will be described in more detail in the following sections.

INTERNAL COMMUNICATION STRUCTURES & PROCEDURES

Internal communication is first and foremost based on the concept of openness and transparency. An active communication strategy is implemented to establish a strong project identity in order to obtain maximum transparency for all partners involved, and to increase synergy in cooperation.

Daily communication among the WPs, the partners, etc. is established mainly through e-mails and a central **mailing list** including all project partners, a **Signal group** for quick communication across teams and partners, a **project space** hosted at the ZSI (Nextcloud) for internal exchange and online storage of all documents as well as offline communication; <https://wolke1.zsi.at/>, **web-conferencing** service (<https://meet.jit.si/CriticalMaking>) for regular online meetings, face-to-face communication (during physical project meetings).

The consortium partners meet regularly to coordinate the progress, either online or face-to-face, if the situation allows for it. Each month, at least one virtual consortium meeting takes place via video conferencing, currently *jitsi*. These meetings ensure internal communication among partners, allow the WP Leaders/thematic leaders to coordinate the various tasks, and report the progress of work to the team members.

During the meeting “live minutes” will be produced and are made accessible to all partners, to view at a later time. Each team reports about the latest updates before a meeting in a shared document, all participants are invited to get an update before the meeting starts and the most relevant issues are then discussed during the meetings. The minutes are available on Nextcloud.

In addition to these virtual consortium meetings, thematic groups (similar to WPs, but overlapping in some cases) may emerge and virtual meetings can be organised by these working groups as well. Similar to the consortium meetings notes and recordings are available on the Nextcloud and each member of the consortium is invited to attend any of these meetings.

EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION STRUCTURES & PROCEDURES

The communication strategy also aims to effectively communicate with parties outside the consortium. Stakeholders will be addressed via the dissemination and communications strategy, which is coordinated by WP7 (Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication) and will be presented in detail in the deliverable **D7.1. Communication, Engagement, and Dissemination (CED) Plan**. Basically, different communication options will be elaborated for the different target groups. The partners of the consortium all have a wide network of contacts, globally, which will serve as a good base for outreaching to different stakeholders.

The communication strategy also aims to effectively communicate with parties outside the consortium, such as other European project consortia, local communities, etc. The coordinator acts as the main interface for any such communication, in close collaboration with the dissemination WP and strategy. However, all partners are involved in such dissemination activities to address their contacts and networks for the purpose of promoting the project and widening the interest group of Critical Making. The main instruments for external communication will be social media and the project website. These channels are coordinated by the partner responsible for WP7, Wikifactory, and strongly supported by GIG.

QUALITY OF (NON-)DELIVERABLES AND PEER REVIEW

A peer-review process for the Critical Making project is set up in order to obtain and guarantee the quality of the deliverables (documentation, reports, etc.) that will be produced during the course of the project and delivered to the European Commission, offered to the Critical Making stakeholders and more globally to the general public. This section describes standards for the Critical Making deliverables and presents the peer-review procedure. A checklist for the deliverables and a template for peer-review reports are given in Appendices to this document. In addition, a template for the policy brief has been provided by the EC. This is also included in the Appendix.

Deliverables

Critical Making deliverables serve different purposes. They are a communication means within the consortium and support the communication with other people outside the consortium. They are aimed at transferring the know-how, to exploit the results and knowledge generated by the project. Deliverables should be written with their target readers in mind. They should be concise and easy to follow. The readability of a document is a vital ingredient for its success. The following general structure should be followed and is as such provided in the deliverable template of the project:

- Cover page
- Amendment History
- List of Authors/Contributors
- Table of Contents
- Abbreviations/Acronyms
- Executive summary
- Introductory part
- Core part
- References
- Annexes (optional)

Annex II includes a checklist that should serve as a guideline when preparing a deliverable. A Critical Making deliverable may be comprised of one or more volumes and may consist of the following parts:

- The main part is the part that summarises the results for high-level executives, technical managers and experts with decision-making competence. It is typically one document and may contain Annexes.

- Annexes are optional and have detailed technical information for experts and implementers. They are added to the main part at the end of the document.

Project deliverables may be classified according to different confidentiality levels, such as public (PU), restricted (RE) or confidential (CO). Following an open access strategy, which the project partners are committed to, all Critical Making deliverables have been classified as PU regarding their dissemination level in the DoA (Description of Action). PU means complete public access and thus, all deliverables will be made available on the project website and specific open repositories, such as Zenodo. In the case consortium members want to change the level of confidentiality of any of the deliverables this requires a decision by the General Assembly and needs to be convincingly argued.

In the following, steps to be taken for publishing a deliverable are listed:

1. These parts form the basis for the deliverable
 - Title and description of the project deliverables
 - The name(s) of the deliverables editor(s)
 - The deliverable history including names(s) of contributors and internal reviewer(s) in charge of the peer review for the deliverable
2. The people appointed to generate parts of the Deliverable – the authors – provide their contribution to the editor.
3. The editor(s) prepare draft 0.1 of the Deliverable by assembling and integrating all contributions. This draft is discussed with all authors. It is recommended to involve the internal reviewers already at this stage.
4. When the editors and the authors are satisfied with the results achieved, the editor issues draft 1.0 and puts it on the Critical Making Nextcloud and sends a note to the consortium.
5. They inform the internal reviewers and ask for a quality check, opinions and constructive comments within a defined deadline (normally one week).
6. The editor deals with all the comments and problems raised, if necessary with the help of the authors. This is a critical phase due to the many interactions involved. It may be necessary to have a meeting (physical, audio- or video conference) in order to speed up the process for reaching a consensus on the amendments.
7. The editor prepares draft 2.0, puts it on the Critical Making Nextcloud and informs the project manager (Dr. Barbara Kieslinger) and the whole consortium that the deliverable has reached final status and can be submitted to the EC and the reviewers.

8. The deliverable is uploaded to the EC reporting portal only by the project manager.

Peer review process

One of the feasible means to enhance the quality of the project deliverables is an internal peer review system. Critical Making deliverables shall be evaluated by 2-3 reviewers so as to gather diversified and balanced viewpoints. Deliverables can be reviewed by members of the core project team or colleagues from the partner institutions as well as invited external experts, for example, Advisory Board members.

Peer reviewers should be nominated by the editor(s) at least 3 weeks before the due date of the deliverable and communicated to the consortium. Nominated peer reviewers can turn down the invitation with clear justification (e.g. lack of expertise) and would thus be requested to nominate another candidate.

Consented peer reviewers are required to produce peer review feedback within 7-10 days after receiving the deliverable from the editor. In case of any expected delay, peer reviewers should notify the editor and the project manager immediately. During the review process, peer reviewers are encouraged to discuss the problems identified in the deliverable with the main author/editor. Peer reviewers are advised to pay particular attention to the following points:

- Is the deliverable aligned with the objectives of the project and relevant work packages?
- Does the deliverable make a significant contribution to the project or not?
- Is the content of the deliverable focused on the intended purpose? Is the content of the deliverable presented in a precise and to-the-point manner?
- Is the length of the deliverable justified? Are there superfluous or irrelevant parts that should be deleted? Are there overlong parts that should be shortened? Are there any parts that are written in flowery language and/or that are unspecific or redundant?
- Are there any grammatical errors and/or typographical errors and/or incomprehensive sentences? Specifically, clear annotations indicating errors and suggested corrections are very helpful for the authors of the deliverable. The annotated deliverable may be sent back to the editor/authors via email together with the peer review report.

- Does the deliverable require substantial revision or rewriting? If yes, it will facilitate the revision process if some concrete suggestions on how to improve the deliverable are given.

Peer review results are described in a peer review report/e-mail (see Annex III), which contains the following information:

- Basic information about the deliverable, author and peer reviewer
- Comments on the length and content of the deliverable
- Major strengths and weaknesses of the deliverable
- Review summary

If minor or substantial revisions are necessary, the authors of the deliverable should make changes and produce the final version of the deliverable before the due submission date. The final responsibility for the content of the deliverable remains with the editor and authors and it is thus their final decision about how to address and integrate the feedback from the peer reviewers. The review reports will be made available internally for the consortium only.

Figure 2: Peer review process

Non-deliverables

For non-deliverables, such as publications and dissemination material, the procedure for deliverables will be used where applicable and with a timeline that fits the material.

Since there are many types of material, this handbook cannot provide details for all cases. We distinguish the following broad categories of material:

- Dissemination material (flyer, website, leaflets, popular science publications, etc.)
The default reviewer is the communication manager, supported by the project manager.

- Scientific publication or conference presentation
Reviewed by one or more team members according to focus and contributions

RISK MANAGEMENT

As stated above, internal surveys and discussions are used to check perceived concerns and risks by all consortium partners. In addition, the quarterly reports that each partner submits online (on Nextcloud) also include a section on possible risks, deviations or corrective actions to be reported to the project management.

The basic risk management methodology to be followed in the project consists of four subsequent steps:

- Risk identification – areas of potential risk are identified and classified.
- Risk quantification – the probability of events is determined and the consequences associated with their occurrence are examined.
- Risk response – methods are produced to reduce or control the risk, e.g. switch to alternative technologies.
- Risk control and report – lessons learned are documented.

Risks with medium or high probability and severe impact are handled with particular caution during the project. At this point, it is expected that the project safely achieves its expected results. This is also supported by the preliminary risk analysis. Normal project risks are managed via “good-practice” project management and rely on the experience from the successful research projects that the partners have been performing. The close supervision and tight control both by the project management and by the various Boards ensure that results are available in time and with adequate quality.

During the proposal writing a first set of risks have been identified and presented with corresponding mitigation measures (Table 4).

Description of risk	Level of likelihood	WPs involved	Proposed risk mitigation measures
Not sufficient participation/interest in co-ideation and co-creation workshops	low	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	The consortium is well connected within the maker community and the first interest has already been confirmed. In case of low participation, we will put more effort into motivation and incentives for participants.

Keeping a balance between researchers' and maker communities' interest	medium	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	Stakeholders from both sides were involved in the writing of this proposal from the beginning, and especially in designing the R&I actions, we think there is a strong will to work together for social good. However, arising problems will be closely monitored and hopefully solved via mediation procedures in the consortium and the case actions.
Methodological framework fails to integrate some relevant methods	medium	WP2, Wp3, WP4, WP5, WP6	There are many potential approaches out there, and we cannot integrate all of them. However, via the internal learning task in WP6 throughout the project, we will identify the most suited methods for our concerns.
Co--creation sessions drive the project into different directions, more efforts needed than originally planned	medium	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	The consortium will keep the necessary flexibility to make adaptations and shifting priorities to a limited extent. The work plan as it is designed now is flexible enough to include such shifts.
A low percentage of submissions for Open Hardware Prize	medium	WP5	A pre-screening of activities in Open Hardware indicates a high submission rate; if this is not reached the call will be adapted to address more relevant topics within the community.
The high effort of translation of data, documentation, interviews, etc.	low	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	The consortium is composed of individuals with a diverse set of language skills and will be able to manage data translation internally; in case of unexpectedly high translation efforts, a translation service will be subcontracted.
Travel bans continue	low	All WPs	While face-to-face interactions are preferred, most of the activities in the

			work plan have been designed in a way to be conducted online.
A partner fails to deliver and stops cooperation	low	All WPs	The consortium consists of highly motivated and reliable partners, all members have extensive networks to replace the unavailable workforce
Work not delivered on time by project partners	low	All WPs	In case of late delivery, the timing needs to be adapted. ZSI and the WP leaders will closely monitor all project activities and send out early warnings.

Table 4: Critical Making risks and mitigation measures

At the kick-off meeting, an additional risk analysis was performed by collecting and discussing the dreams and fears of consortium members on an interactive Miro Board (https://miro.com/app/board/o9J_IZ5-_U8=/). The following image summarises on the one hand, the dreams and expectations and on the other hand the fears and risks associated with it. During the course of the project, all partners will follow up on these aspects and reflect on contingencies should any of the identified risks, or emerging risks, start having an influence on the activities progress.

Figure 3: Dreams, fears and questions to other partners

In the course of the project, management is responsible for close monitoring of the overall progress and risk identification. Risk identification is however also collaboratively encouraged as part of reflective sessions during the project meetings. Early communication of risks is encouraged as well as discussions, in order to achieve a profound understanding of risks. The project management promotes an open communication culture to openly discuss any issues arising.

PROJECT TEMPLATES

Critical Making intends to use a consistent 'project style'. This is implemented by providing templates for deliverables and reports, presentations, posters and other dissemination and communication material. More project-style templates can be produced by the communication and outreach team when needed.

All available project style templates are available on the shared workspace on Nextcloud.

TOOLS AND COLLABORATION INFRASTRUCTURE

Internal

While the previous section was concerned with the processes of communication and collaboration there is also a technical side to this and a number of technical tools are used to provide the Critical Making collaboration infrastructure. It consists of several pieces:

- The Critical Making mailing list is used for project-wide asynchronous communication. The address of the mailing list is: criticalmaking@lists.zsi.at
- Signal for ad-hoc communication to the whole team as well as to different subgroups and individual team member: Critical Making @ Signal
- Jitsi is used for regular web conferencing: <https://meet.jit.si/CriticalMaking>
- Nextcloud (<https://wolke1.zsi.at/>) is used for sharing files and for real-time co-creation of documents
- e-mail and telephone are used for bilateral communication
- Critical Making Website (<https://criticalmaking.eu/>) is the main portal for sharing our research with different target groups and generally presenting our work to the public

The choice for this collaboration structure has been made taking into consideration practical aspects as well as privacy and data protection issues related to the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Nextcloud Workspace interface for 'Critical Making!'. The interface shows a breadcrumb trail, a search bar, and a file list table. The file list includes folders and files with their respective sizes and modification dates.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Size	Modified
<input type="checkbox"/>	Communications	38.2 MB	19 hours ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	Deliverables	641 KB	7 minutes ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	Events	2.9 MB	a month ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	Literature	133.1 MB	a month ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	Management	11.4 MB	15 days ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	meetings	16.7 MB	12 days ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	proposal final	52.2 MB	2 months ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	WP3 Gender	24 KB	5 days ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	Case_Study_Template_v1.xlsx	17 KB	7 days ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	Readme.md	< 1 KB	2 months ago

8 folders and 3 files (including 1 hidden) 255.2 MB

Figure 4: Nextcloud Workspace for Critical Making

External

For external collaboration the project coordinator has the responsibility to provide appropriate infrastructure, which will be jointly agreed with the consortium partners and especially the WP7 leader. External collaboration is part of the Communication, Engagement and Dissemination Plan (D7.1) and is jointly executed. This includes collaboration with other projects in the SwafS programme and with other researchers and stakeholders outside of the programme.

The project coordinator is also responsible for any communication with the European Commission (EC). The main collaboration interface with the EC is the Participant Portal available at <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/>. It is the main site for technical and financial reporting as well as any other contractual actions.

GENDER AND FAMILY CONSIDERATIONS

The Consortium commits itself to supporting the European Union policy on equal opportunities across gender. To this end, equal participation of all genders at all levels of the project, including management, is continually encouraged and supported. Project staff of all Consortium participants and linked third parties is composed according to the principle of equal opportunity and all member organisations strongly enforce human resources equal opportunity policy. Most co-operation between project partners will be handled via digital networks and phone conferences, minimising the number of long-distance journeys thereby facilitating the participation of parents and other care givers. Likewise, phone conferences will be scheduled to be family friendly. The location, as well as the schedule, of meetings and events should be chosen to be **appropriate to childcare needs, with childcare services being sought near meetings if requested.**

For all project activities the consortium will do its utmost to have an equal gender distribution for e.g. interviews, workshops, co-design sessions, stakeholder encounters, and the Advisory Board.

RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (RRI)

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and its current practices in maker communities are core research aspects of Critical Making. Thus, we will be looking at RRI from a critical research perspective. Net to this research focus on RRI, we also follow RRI principles in our own research work and briefly elaborate on some core research principles we want to follow in this project.

In order to conduct our own research in a responsible and ethical way and for the very practical purpose of this handbook, we still find it useful to consider the contested six key dimensions of RRI as defined by the European Commission (Jacob et al., 2013):

- **Governance:** Governance of policymakers to prevent harmful or unethical developments in research and innovation
- **Open Access:** Open access to research results and publications to boost innovation and increase the use of scientific results
- **Ethics:** Research must respect ethical standards and fundamental rights to respond to societal challenges
- **Gender:** Gender equality and in a wider sense diversity

- **Public Engagement:** Engagement of all societal actors (researchers, industry, policy makers, civil society) in a reflective research process
- **Science education:** Enhancement of current education processes to better equip future researchers and society as a whole with the necessary competencies to participate in research processes

In addition to these key dimensions, which are reflected in the European policy agendas, RRI can also be defined with regards to its process requirements which include **openness and transparency, anticipation and reflection, responsiveness and adaptive change and diversity and inclusion.** Figure 5 which stems from the RRI-Tools project¹ where the ZSI has been a core partner, shows an integrative view on these two perspectives, which complement each other.

Figure 5: Overview of key dimensions and process requirements of RRI according to RRI-Tools project

In the following, we briefly describe the six key dimensions and how they relate to our own research practices in Critical Making.

GOVERNANCE

Among the six key dimensions of RRI, governance has a slightly different function compared to the others, as it is rather an organising and steering principle that determinates the success of all other RRI dimensions and integrates them. In other words, RRI relies on good governing structures for the promotion of RRI. Governance methods range from foresight techniques (scenario studies, value-sensitive design, etc.), assessment (ethical committees, needs assessment, technology assessment, etc.),

¹ <http://www.rri-tools.eu>

agenda-setting (consultation, co-creation, etc.) to regulation (code of conduct, policies, funding guidelines, etc.).

Governance of RRI is rarely seen on a project level; it is rather applied on funding level or within organisations, e.g. to call for organisation-wide RRI guidelines and policies. The Critical Making project can be perceived as an attempt to tackle RRI on a project level. However, comprehensive RRI guidelines for projects are still missing and thus this handbook will aim at meeting this need. Also, it has to be acknowledged that governance structures need to be at least on an institutional level in order to be sustainable. On a project level, however, it makes sense to break down what RRI in the specific context means and how it can be adapted to the project particularities.

OPEN ACCESS

In the narrower sense, open access is about enabling or giving access to research results and publications to the public. It addresses only the final stage of research activity, the publication and dissemination phase. With the launch of Horizon 2020, it has become mandatory to follow open access publication strategies (European Commission, 2012).

Open access is not identical with open science, open innovation and open data, although there are obvious overlaps. For instance, in contrast, to open access, open science implies opening up the whole science process in real time to the public, from choosing areas to investigate in, formulating the research questions to choosing the methods, collecting data and finally discussing the results. Open science means democratising science and research, usually through ICT.

When talking about open access in the context of Critical Making we refer to open access in the narrower sense. Our project will basically follow an open access publication strategy, but will also make data available to the public at an earlier stage where suitable (c.f. chapter 6).

ETHICS

The European Commission defines ethics as a key dimension of RRI as follows:

“European society is based on shared values. In order to adequately respond to societal challenges, research and innovation must respect fundamental rights and the highest ethical standards. Beyond the mandatory legal aspects, this aims to ensure increased societal relevance and acceptability of research and innovation outcomes. Ethics should

not be perceived as a constraint to research and innovation, but rather as a way of ensuring high quality results.” (p.4)²

Ethics thereby shall not be perceived as a constraint but rather as a guiding principle to help ensure high quality outcomes and to justify decisions. This is also the case for Critical Making. We will deal with the three main aspects of ethics as defined by the European Commission (2015), namely 1) Research integrity and good research practice, 2) Research ethics for the protection of research objects, and 3) Societal relevance and ethical acceptability of research and innovation outcomes.

Ethics further implies social justice and inclusion aspects: The widest range of societal actors and civil society shall benefit from research and innovation outcomes. In other words, products and services as a result of Research & Innovation (R&I) activities shall be acceptable and affordable for different social groups, which is also a special goal of Critical Making.

Ethics is an integral part of responsible research, from the conceptual phase to the publication of research results. The consortium of Critical Making is clearly committed to showing appreciation of potential ethical issues that may arise during the course of the project and has as such defined a set of procedures on how to deal with ethics in a responsible way.

The main aspects the project is dealing with in regards to ethics are the protection of identity, privacy, obtaining informed consent and communicating benefits and risks to the involved target groups. The activities performed in Critical Making may include data collection from individuals and organisations remotely as well as on-site. In the following, we outline the basic processes of ethical compliance of the project with a general view on the scientific data collection.

Recruiting process and informed consent procedures

Critical Making initiatives involve human participants. We plan to engage makers and quadruple helix stakeholders to participate actively in the project research activities, such as case studies, surveys, interviews and workshops. During the project activities, we will ensure respect for human beings, human dignity and fair distribution of the benefits of the research. To protect the values, rights, and interests of the research

²http://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/document_library/pdf_06/responsible-research-and-innovation-leaflet_en.pdf

participants, information notices will be handed out in advance, clarifying the aims, methods and implication of the research as well as the ability of each participant to terminate the participation at any given time without consequences. In case of site-specific case actions, information will be given in simple regional language.

More precisely, the members of the Critical Making consortium that will be engaged in the case actions will take all the necessary steps to ensure that participants are aware of the evaluation process and the related tasks as well as the aims and the objectives of the evaluation process.

Informed consent forms will be provided to ensure that participants have understood the information provided. Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets in the language and terms intelligible to the participants will be kept on file.

The engaged participants will be requested to carefully read the details outlined in an information sheet, and to sign a written and freely given informed consent form, which will be prepared in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) and all national relevant data and privacy protection regulations, prior to their inclusion in the studies.

They will also clearly introduce the role of the researchers and the role of the participants, and provide practical information. This defining of roles is of great importance in cases where the role is dual (i.e. in the co-design). The participants will be clearly informed in cases where their activity is video-recorded or their interactions are monitored.

Additional practical details concerning the duration of the evaluation activities will be also given. This is to ensure that the project makes every effort to abide by the Directive 95/46/EC for the protection of personal data that describes that participants should:

- be asked to consent with the processing of data that are gathered during presence sessions or that result from their online activities within the Critical Making ecosystem (article 7)
- be informed that restrictions to the processing apply (article 8)
- be informed that they may access those data at all times (article 12)

The right of any participant to withdraw from the evaluation activities at any time is also recognised.

For some activities, especially in WP4, the project will involve children 12 years and older as these activities are dedicated specifically to a young audience. In the activities in WP4, the participants are subject to only minimal risk and burden and the results of the research will benefit the individual or group represented by the participant.

Given the direct participation of under-aged students, it will be ensured that the school policy on this matter is explicitly followed. Additionally:

- Only students whose parents/ legally authorised representatives have provided informed approval and consent will be included in the activities. We ensure that they have sufficient information to enable them to provide this on behalf and in the best interests of the participants by providing the text in an understandable local language.
- Whenever possible, the assent of the participants will be obtained in addition to the consent of the parents or legal representatives. Participants will be asked for consent if they reach the age of majority in the course.
- The participants will be introduced to the activities in an age-appropriate manner
- Participants' rights to privacy, safety and self-determination will be respected
- Focus group interviews will be used as they might be less intimidating compared to individual interviews
- Only age-appropriate online tools and content will be introduced
- Anonymity and confidentiality will be ensured
- The collected data will be used appropriately and kept securely in files by the consortium partners dealing with the data analysis (i.e., primarily TUB). If the data needs to be transported physically or virtually via computer networks, proper encryption will be applied.
- Technologies will be applied to minimise the risk of data misuse in the unlikely case that the data is lost.
- Data collected during teaching and training episodes will be discussed with teachers before any publication takes place

In regard to the informed approval consent, specific statements should be included in the relevant information sheets as part of the Consent Forms Targeting Parents:

1. Who is conducting the study
2. What are the objectives of the study
3. How were they selected to participate in the study
4. What do participants need to do and how long will it take

5. How the data will be used
6. How the findings will be documented and published
7. How they will be informed of the results

Data protection and privacy, personal data handling

During any data collection process, data protection issues with regards to handling personal data will be addressed by the following strategies:

Participants, who volunteer to be enrolled in our activities, will be exhaustively informed so that they are able to autonomously decide whether they consent to participate or not. The purposes of the research, the procedures as well as the handling of their data (protection, storage) will be explained. For online interviews, these explanations will be a part of the initial briefing of interviewees. For face-to-face interventions, informed consent (see Annex) shall be agreed upon and signed by both, the study participants as well as the respective research partner.

The data exploitation will be in line with the respective national data protection acts. Since data privacy is under threat when data is traced back to individuals – they may become identifiable and the data may be abused – to mitigate this risk, we will anonymise/psudomise all data.

Data gathered through questionnaires, interviews, observational studies, focus groups, workshops and other possible data gathering methods during this research will be anonymised and therefore the data cannot be traced back to the individual. Data will be stored only in anonymous forms so the identities of the participants will only be known by the research partners involved. Raw data like interview protocols and audio files will be shared within the consortium partners only after having signed the confidentiality agreement (see Annex I). Reports based on interviews, focus groups and other data gathering methods will be based on aggregated information and will comprise anonymous quotations respectively.

The collected data will be stored on password-protected servers at the partner institution responsible for data collection and analysis. The data will be used only within the project and will not be made accessible for any third party, unless anonymised. Sensitive data or personal will not be stored after the end of the project (incl. the time for final publications) unless required by specific national legislation.

The stored data do not contain the names or addresses of participants and will be edited for full anonymity before being processed (e.g. in project reports).

Critical Making will obtain and handle personal data during the project. Formalized questionnaires and transcribed interview data will be stored at the local level and pseudo-anonymization will be applied. Audio recordings of interviews will be destroyed after transcription. Every subject name will be replaced by a unique study number - ID code. At the end of the study, the data collection will eventually be made publicly accessible after a process of anonymization on ZENODO.

The informed consent requirements for this will be evaluated at the beginning of the study. Data collection and storage will be subject to the national rules implementing the data protection general regulation (as after the implementation of the GDPR different national legal instruments are going to be implemented).

The following procedures will be included in the research protocol to safeguard the privacy of study subjects and prevent unauthorised access:

- Reported study results will pertain to analyses of aggregate data. No individual's name will be associated with any published or unpublished report of this study;
- Data may be processed only if it is really adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for this research, following the 'data minimisation principle'
- Personal information, including questionnaires and interview data, will be safely stored locally in secure facilities, and names will be replaced by unique study numbers - ID code stored separately. Primary databases and analysis files will be stored on computers with personal identifiers removed. In each of the partner organizations, a person will be appointed as responsible for the data, and they will coordinate with the project Data Protection Officer (DPO).
 - Hard copies of consent forms will be stored in a locked archive at the partners' premises and shredded upon expiry or withdrawal. No files will be copied and transferred to computers for personal use. The consent form and information sheet, which will be prepared, shall be in a language and will use terms fully understandable to the potential participants. Participants are asked to read, fill in, date and sign it in written declaring that they have read and understood the information.
 - ID will link all basic data required for the study and will be stored in password protected computer files. Access to these files will be limited to authorized project personnel.
 - In the case that participants will provide their contact details (telephone, e-mail address) after having given their consent to participating and having agreed to be

re-contacted for research purposes, this information will be stored in password protected computer files. Access to these files will be limited to authorized project personnel, whose names will be communicated to participants.

- Hard copy records or computer-generated records containing personally identifiable information will be stored in locked cabinets in an office with limited access.
- The project personnel will be informed in the importance of confidentiality of individual records and required to sign a confidentiality agreement.
- An acknowledgment of the contribution of interviewees or other kinds of participation will be integrated in the publications.

The coordinator, ZSI, has appointed a Data Protection Officer, Wolfgang Michalek, who can be contacted under: data-protection@zsi.at. This information will be made available to all data subjects (participants) according to the procedures defined in the data management plan.

Communication strategy

Study participants will be made aware of the potential benefits and identified risks of participating in the project at all times.

The main means of communicating benefits and risks to the individual is the informed consent (see Annex). Prior to consent, each individual participant in any of the studies in Critical Making will be clearly informed of its goals, its possible adverse events, and the possibility to refuse to enter or to retract at any time with no consequences. This will be done through a project information sheet or the informed consent form and it will be reinforced verbally.

In order to make sure that participants are able to recall what they agree upon when signing, the informed consent forms will be provided in the native language of the participants. In addition, the consortium partners will make sure that the informed consent is written in a language suitable for the target group(s). Different informed consents will be made available, e.g. consent of adult participants, parental consent, informed assent for children/minors.

For media material (e.g. photos, videos) produced during any of the Critical Making events, a media waiver will be distributed to participants to make sure that participants are aware of this and agree/disagree with the production and use of such material by the project partners. A template for the waiver is provided in the Annex IV of this document.

Informed consent/informed assent

As stated above informed consent/assent will be collected from all participants involved in Critical Making studies. The declaration of consent forms is provided in the Annex.

Relevant regulations and scientific standards

The consortium is following European regulations and scientific standards to perform ethical research. The following lists some of the basic regulations and guidelines.

The Critical Making project will fully respect the citizens' rights as reported by EGE and as proclaimed in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000/C 364/01), having as its main goal to enhance and to foster the participation of European citizens to education, regardless of cultural, linguistic or social backgrounds. Regarding the personal data collected during the research, the project will make every effort to heed the rules for the protection of personal data as described in Directive 95/46/EC³.

In addition, the consortium is following the following European Regulations and Guidelines:

- The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union:
http://www.europarl.europa.eu/charter/default_en.htm
- European Convention on Human Rights and it's Supplementary Protocols
http://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Convention_ENG.pdf
- Horizon 2020 ethics self-assessment
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/doc/call/h2020/h2020-msca-itn-2015/1620147-h2020_-_guidance_ethics_self_assess_en.pdf
- EU Code of Ethics: <http://www.respectproject.org/ethics/412ethics.pdf>
- European Textbook on Ethics in Research
https://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/document_library/pdf_06/textbook-on-ethics-report_en.pdf
- European data protection legislation http://ec.europa.eu/justice/data-protection/index_en.htm
- RESPECT Code of Practice for Socio-Economic Research
<http://www.respectproject.org/code/index.php?id=de>
- Code of Ethics of the International Sociological Association (ISA)
http://www.isa-sociology.org/about/isa_code_of_ethics.htm

³ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=URISERV%3A114012>

- The Nuremberg Code (1946) addressing volunteer consent and proper acting
- The Revised Declaration of Helsinki in its last version of 2013
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and its implementations at Member States level
- UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (1990)
- The New Brunswick Declaration: A Declaration on Research Ethics, Integrity and Governance resulting from the 1st Ethics Rupture Summit, Fredericton, New Brunswick, Canada (2013)
- The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, Revised Edition, by ALLEA - All European Academies 2017
- Ten principles of Citizen Science of the European Citizen Science Association: https://ecsa.citizenscience.net/sites/default/files/ecsa_ten_principles_of_citizen_science.pdf

National and Local Regulations and Standards

In addition to the more general and EU-wide guidelines, project partners have to adhere to, and respect, national regulations and laws as well as to research organisational ethical approval as requested by their own institutions. All partners are aware of their responsibilities in that respect and will follow the respective guidelines.

GENDER

Gender equality generally means equal rights, opportunities, and responsibilities for both genders so that individuals can exploit and realise their full potentials independently from their sex. In Critical Making, we clearly want to move away from a binary concept of gender, which is still very often prevailing in academic gender actions. In Critical Making, gender is regarded as fluid and we aim to explore opportunities for all genders in the specific WP3, dedicated to gender aspects.

Gender equality as a key dimension of RRI comprises two main aspects (European Commission, 2015), namely to strive for gender-balanced teams in research and innovation (at operational as well as at decision making level) and the inclusion and integration of gender perspectives in research and innovation content and process. Gender analysis and gender monitoring throughout the project shall aim at looking at both aspects of gender equality, at the human capital dimension (where possible, apart from institutional conditions) and the research aspect of gender (Föger et al., 2016). With our focus on gender in WP5, we clearly cover the latter.

When it comes to internal processes, such as the composition of project teams, of work package leaders, of the advisory group, the use of gender-sensitive language and the awareness of producing gender-sensitive content is important.

In line with the Toolkit on Gender in EU-funded research (European Commission, 2009) Critical Making will strive at doing gender-sensitive innovation. Particularly in the following project steps gender has to be addressed and taken into account:

Project design and methodology: we will make sure that for any of our approaches in co-design and other engagement activities, we will aim at representative data in the sense that different gender perspectives will be described, where relevant.

Project implementation: Data-collection tools such as questionnaires, interview guidelines, etc. need to be gender sensitive and use gender-neutral language and have to allow for differentiation between gender perspectives. In the evaluation data analysis, we will particularly pay attention to whether there are differences in gender, for instance, in terms of artifacts that are produced, in terms of communicating and sharing, etc.

Dissemination phase – reporting of data: We will use gender-neutral language in our publications. Furthermore, we will sensitively decide which visual materials to use. In addition, we will aim at publishing gender-specific results.

SCIENCE EDUCATION

Science education under the RRI umbrella is meant to meet several objectives (European Commission, 2015; Föger et al., 2016):

- To empower the society to critically reflect and to improve on their skills to be able to challenge research, thus to make them “science-literate” (in this sense, there is a great overlap with the key dimension of public engagement)
- To enhance future researchers and other societal actors to become good RRI actors
- To make science attractive to children and teenagers with the purpose to promote science careers, especially in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics)
- To close the gap between science and education. There is still a significant distance between the two areas.

Co-design is regarded as a possible empowering tool for science education as it enables participants to shape the development of certain technologies or services according to the RRI-Tools project. In Critical Making, we plan to include children in the co-design

process for certain activities. WP4 is specifically dedicated to a young audience. Educational activities and student engagement are thus an integral part of the WP4 activities. They are targeted at children of 12 years and beyond. The maker spaces involved in the Critical Making project regularly offer educational activities to young people and schools as the maker movement has started to get attention from schools and educational authorities.

PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT

In recent years, science communication has moved from the one-way-communication approach to basically inform the general public towards public engagement, which means more elaborate and active involvement of citizens leading to collaboration and empowerment.

There is a vast range of tools and methods with different levels of participation available, e.g. public consultations, public deliberations for decision making, public participation in R&I processes, Citizen Science, etc. The goal by opening up research and innovation processes to the public is to better meet the values, needs and expectations of society and thus to improve R&I and to find solutions to the so-called grand challenges that society is facing (Cagnin, Amanatidou, & Keenan, 2012).

Thus, realising this key dimension of RRI is an important goal in Critical Making and WP7 is working on a strategy to define and execute the engagement and communication strategy of the project in an inclusive way. In our engagement strategy we want to stress **diversity** as a concept that includes gender, age, ethnicity, cultural background, minority groups, etc. In Critical Making we consider diversity as a key in our engagement and recruitment process.

RRI MANAGEMENT IN CRITICAL MAKING

The notion of Responsible Research and Innovation does not offer a checklist or one universal guideline on how to do RRI. It is also not in the spirit of RRI to have such a fixed set of measures, as RRI is rather perceived as a process that requires continuous questioning and reflection. Thus, mechanisms have to be installed and embedded in the project to stimulate the reflection of the consortium and to keep these alive throughout the lifetime of the project. As RRI is in the nature of our project, Critical Making is committed to the integrative concept of RRI and plans to act accordingly in our own research. We will learn from our participatory interventions on RRI aspects in

makerspaces also for our own work and reflect on that regularly in the consortium meetings.

In order to stimulate reflection and deliberation on RRI and to keep these alive we have foreseen these main instruments:

- ethical guidelines, including forms for informed consent and confidentiality agreement
- the Open Data Management Plan
- RRI-related workshops such as the cross-action learning workshop on RRI in WP6

OPEN SCIENCE, OPEN ACCESS AND OPEN RESEARCH DATA

The project firmly believes in openness to be a major factor for innovation and this was also one of the main motivations for Critical Making, which promotes openness in a dedicated work package. Openness has many facets. The most important ones for the Critical Making research process are, following Carlos Moedas's (European Commissioner for Research, Science and Innovation) strategy of the 3 Os, Open Science, Open Innovation and Open Data⁴:

Open project collaboration. All partners are committed to developing (working) relationships with external partners for mutual benefit. Making contacts with similar projects and establishing collaboration is considered beneficial for all. Open collaboration in Critical Making is understood in a trans-disciplinary way, opening innovation processes to the wider public and allowing new forms of collaboration as intended in the co-design activities of the project.

Open source technology. From a scientific perspective, the project looks at openness in relation to **open source hardware**. The main aim is to investigate existing experiences with new experimental, participatory interventions to discover interrelations between openness and other RRI principles and try to find answers as to how actors in the maker movement interpret social responsibility with regards to open hardware business models, whether there are tensions between the core values of

⁴ http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_SPEECH-15-4532_de.htm

sharing and openness and new open source business models and how these tensions can be mitigated.

Citizen Science. In its broad definition, “*Citizen science actively involves the public in scientific research that generates new knowledge or understanding, and thus has the potential to bring together science, policy makers, and society as a whole in an impactful way. As a core dimension of Open Science, it opens up the opportunity for all members of society to take an active role in research, innovation and the development of evidence-based policy, at local, national and EU levels*“ as stated on the European Citizen Science portal EU-Citizen.Science (<https://eu-citizen.science/about/>). Thus, we also understand the co-design and knowledge co-production process that is taking place in Critical Making as part of a Citizen Science approach.

Open access to scientific results. From a scientific perspective, the consortium clearly favours open access to its scientific output, which is supported by several project members’ internal policies of supporting open access in general.

Open access to research data. Critical Making is part of a pilot action on open access to research data and is thus committed to providing access not only to project results and processes, but also to data collected during that process. Although the general policy of the Critical Making project is to apply “open by default” to its research data, we have to handle privacy issues with special care. Legal rules on anonymity, as described above, are thus highly relevant and need to be agreed upon with each of the participants. In case of a doubt, the data privacy of our participants always prevails over open data policy.

Critical Making is part of the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP), a pilot action on open access to research data, which requires projects to define and execute a data management plan. In month 6 we will deliver an open data management plan for Critical Making. The open access strategy will be detailed in the following sections.

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

OPEN ACCESS STRATEGY FOR PUBLICATIONS

In line with the EC policy initiative on open access⁵, which refers to the practice of granting free Internet access to research articles, the project is committed to following a publication strategy considering a mix of both 'Green open access' (immediate or delayed open access that is provided through self-archiving) and 'Gold open access' (immediate open access that is provided by a publisher) as far as possible.

All deliverables labelled as “public” will be made accessible via the Critical Making website (<https://criticalmaking.eu/>). The publications stemming from the project work will also be made available on the website as far as it does not infringe the publisher’s rights as well as on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>).

All outcomes of the project labelled as “public” will be distributed under a specific free/open license, where the authors retain the authors’ rights but the users can redistribute the content freely. The following are a few relevant sources for deciding on the specific license for each outcome:

- Data:
 - A definition of Open Data: <http://opendefinition.org/>
 - Licenses: <http://opendefinition.org/licenses/>
- Software:
 - Free Software
 - The definition: <http://www.gnu.org/philosophy/free-sw.html>
 - Licenses: <http://www.gnu.org/licenses/licenses.html>
 - Open Source Software:
 - The definition: <https://opensource.org/osd-annotated>
 - Licenses: <https://opensource.org/licenses>
- Reports, publications, media:
 - Creative Commons
 - Explanation: <https://creativecommons.org/about/>
 - Licenses: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>
 - Choose a license: <https://creativecommons.org/choose/>
 - Sharing publications on the project website and via Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/>

⁵

<http://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/index.cfm?fuseaction=public.topic&id=1294&lang=1>

Data management plan (DMP)

A data management plan (DMP) is an important instrument for the work in Critical Making as it describes the project's data management policy in detail. The DMP evolves in the course of the project and will be updated accordingly as data is collected. There will be an extra deliverable for the DMP, which is due in Month 6 and this upcoming document will include the necessary level of details for the data management of the project

To summarise, the main open access points for Critical Making data, publications, and innovation are:

- The project website: www.careables.org
- Zenodo: <http://www.zenodo.org/>
- OpenAIRE <https://www.openaire.eu/> for depositing publications and research data

OPEN ACCESS AND OPEN DATA HANDLING PROCESS

The internal procedures to grant open access to any publication, research data or other innovation stemming from the Critical Making project (e.g. technology), are following a lightweight structure, while respecting ethical issues at all times.

The main workflow starts at the WP level, where each team is responsible for respecting ethical procedures at all times during the data gathering and processing steps. The WP/working team members are also responsible for any data anonymization, if applicable. An agreement has to be reached within the team for making any outcome openly available; the final approval is done by the Project Management Board (see Figure 6):

Figure 6: Open Access work flow

Due to the nature of the project, the Data Management Plan may have to be revised during the course of project activities. As the co-design approach is a rather dynamic methodology it is not possible to clearly specify all data sources and collected outcomes from the beginning.

CONCLUSIONS

This handbook describes the main procedures of the Critical Making project to operate successfully and effectively in order to achieve high quality project results following a responsible research and innovation (RRI) approach. Open access, ethics, and engagement of all societal actors are amongst the key elements of the European RRI framework (European Union, 2012). Critical Making is clearly committed to responding to societal challenges in a responsible way by itself, given its main objective of open healthcare, and by the way, the actions in the project are conducted.

While this handbook is provided in the form of a report and deliverable, it is a living document in the sense of being updated and challenged by the consortium in the course of the project. The processes described here are implemented in the daily work of the consortium and most of the elements (e.g. the forms for informed consent, data management plan, etc.) are separately available on the collaboration infrastructure such as Nextcloud.

The management reports will include updates on any crucial changes in the handbook as well as on the results of specific measures such as the internal RRI reflections or any additional elements added to the project structure related to high quality responsible research.

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ANNEX I CONFIDENTIALITY AGREEMENT

CONFIDENTIALITY AGREEMENT

Research data shared between the researchers in the Critical Making project may contain personal identifiable information (PII), the usage of which is protected by law. To comply with this law, usage and sharing of data is restricted and it is essential that you follow the rules and guidelines described in the ethical guidelines defined for Critical Making for collecting, processing, sharing and storage of data.

In addition to this you are obliged to comply with the following terms:

I will not share the participant data, collected by the project team, in which I am in receipt with any third parties, including the case study organisations, employers of the participants, or other members of the consortium of the Critical Making project without explicit, written consent from the person(s) who provided the data.

Where relevant, I will instruct the people for whom I have responsibility who have access to the data of the relevant ethical protocols and ensure that they follow the guidelines defined for the project, as listed below.

I will delete the data at least _____ months after the project outcomes have been published (recommended time is 3 months).

Declaration: I hereby declare my consent with the rules outlined above:

Date:.....

Name & Organisation:

Signature:

List of persons in my organisation who have access to the data:

ANNEX II CHECKLIST FOR DELIVERABLES

1. Overall technical evaluation of the deliverable

- Does the deliverable contain new, or value added information?
- Are there any major technical errors, omissions, lack of necessary details?
- How do the results compare with the state of the art and/or parallel activities?
- What value does the document add to the project partners?

2. Executive summary

- Are the following questions clearly asked and answered?
- Which problem(s) and key questions of interest to intended readers are addressed?
- What are the expected main benefits of this deliverable?
- What are the results contained in this deliverable?
- Who are the main consumers for this deliverable, e.g. who should read it?
- Why should I read the deliverable?
- Suggestions/recommendations for follow-up actions by project participants and/or by the general public.
- Is the length acceptable for the executive summary (e.g. approx. 2 pages)?

3. Introduction

- Is the purpose of the document clearly stated?
- Is the technical subject properly introduced?
- If necessary, is there a guide to the reader (document structure, a short description of chapters and relationships)?
- If necessary, are there statements on the technical assumption, readers' prerequisites, relationships with other documents or parallel activities?

4. Main part of the deliverable

- Does it contain what was defined in the deliverable description in the DoA?
- If something has been left out, have clear and valid reasons been given as to why?
- Is the key part structured in a logical way?
- Is the content appropriate for the intended audience? Does it only include essential information?
- Does it duplicate or contradict standards or other on-going known initiatives? If yes, the affected standard or initiatives need to be identified.
- Is the length acceptable (approx. 30 pages for the main part)?

5. Conclusion

- Are conclusions reached? Are they within the consortium perspective?
- Are any necessary follow-up actions clearly indicated?
- Are the conclusions consistent with the executive summary?
- Should this Deliverable be

- Utilised by other projects?
- Released (in full or part) to the Associated Partner Network or to PES initiatives such as PES-to-PES dialogue?

6. Annexes (optional)

- Are they complete in all parts?
- Relevant for the content described in the deliverable?

ANNEX III PEER REVIEW TEMPLATE

Instructions: Peer reviewers should fill out all six sections in this template and send the completed template to the editor/main author on or before the specified due date.

1. Basic Information

Deliverable Nr & Title:

Main Author/Editor:

Peer Reviewer (Institution, Person):

Date of Receipt of Deliverable:

Date of Sending out the completed peer review:

2. Length of the deliverable

Is the length of the deliverable justified? – YES - NO

If no, please specify by e.g. indicating parts that are superfluous, irrelevant, redundant, unspecific or would need more explanation?

3. Content

Does the deliverable meet the objectives of the deliverable described in the respective Work Package Work Description? – YES - NO

If not, please indicate the parts where improvement is necessary.

Is the content of the deliverable focused and presented in a precise and to-the-point manner? – YES - NO

If not, please indicate the parts where improvement is necessary.

Does the deliverable require substantial revision or rewriting? – YES - NO

If yes, please give concrete suggestions on how to improve the deliverable.

4. Major strengths

5. Major weaknesses

6. Review Summary

The current version of the deliverable is []:

I: applicable and ready to be submitted to the EC, if required;

2: applicable, but requires minor revisions;

3: inapplicable and requires substantial revisions.

Is it necessary for the revised deliverables to be reviewed again before submitting it to the EC (1:Yes, 2: No)? []

Other remarks:

ANNEX IV MEDIA WAIVER

I hereby grant the {Name of Organization} permission to use my likeness in a photograph, video, or other digital media (“photo”) in any and all of its publications, including web-based publications, without payment or other consideration.

I understand and agree that all photos will become the property of the {Name of Organization} and will not be returned.

I hereby irrevocably authorize the {Name of Organization} to edit, alter, copy, exhibit, publish, or distribute these photos for any lawful purpose. In addition, I waive any right to inspect or approve the finished product wherein my likeness appears. Additionally, I waive any right to royalties or other compensation arising or related to the use of the photo.

I hereby hold harmless, release, and forever discharge the {Name of Organization} from all claims, demands, and causes of action which I, my heirs, representatives, executors, administrators, or any other persons acting on my behalf or on behalf of my estate have or may have by reason of this authorization.

I HAVE READ AND UNDERSTAND THE ABOVE PHOTO RELEASE. I AFFIRM THAT I AM AT LEAST 18 YEARS OF AGE, OR, IF I AM UNDER 18 YEARS OF AGE, I HAVE OBTAINED THE REQUIRED CONSENT OF MY PARENTS/LEGAL GUARDIANS AS EVIDENCED BY THEIR SIGNATURES BELOW. I ACCEPT:

Print Name: _____

Signature: _____ | Date: ___ / ___ / _____

If under 18, a parent/legal guardian must sign:

Parent/legal guardian Signature: _____ | Date: ___ / ___ / _____

ANNEX V POLICY BRIEF TEMPLATE

Ref. Ares(2021)1428131 - 23/02/2021

EUROPEAN POLICYBRIEF

LOGO of the project

TITLE

Short description of the document's subject

DATE

INTRODUCTION

The objectives of the Swaf5 part of Horizon 2020 are to build effective co-operation between science and society, foster the recruitment of new talent for science, and to pair scientific excellence with social awareness and responsibility. There are eight lines of actions (science careers, gender equality, public engagement, science education, open access/open data, governance and ethics, the precautionary principle, science communication), all of which are pertinent to reaching the Swaf5' objectives.

The Swaf5 Work Programmes have included a range of topics that may be characterised as being relatively open ('bottom-up') or closed ('prescriptive'), the choice of which has depended on the area of activity, the policy/research demands, and awareness of the need to open up space for creativity and good ideas to flow from applicants on transdisciplinary issues of concern. Even with this balance of open and closed topics, it is necessary to create space for ideas that fill gaps, 'connect the dots' between projects, activities and objectives, or focus on innovative or emerging issues that have so far not been broached.

The projects funded under this topic are completely bottom-up ('open') - a challenge to applicants to propose innovative research and innovation actions that are needed to help meet Swaf5 objectives. Activities to involve stakeholders from all parts of the quadruple helix within the research and innovation activities will be favoured. R&I outcomes should help build effective cooperation between science and society, foster the recruitment of new talent for science, and pair scientific excellence with social awareness and responsibility.

EVIDENCE AND ANALYSIS

[Outline your most policy-relevant findings in relation to the policy context described in the introduction. The Evidence and Analysis section of the policy brief should support the recommendations that follow – 1 page]

- EUROPEANPOLICYBRIEF -
Page | 1

POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

[In bullet points, state the policy implications of your findings in relation with the results and, where appropriate, offer recommendations. – half a page]

SUSTAINABILITY AND LEGACY

[Indicate any project output e.g. toolkit or guidelines, worth promoting amongst other projects in the field – a couple of lines]

PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

[Describe the project's objectives and methodology including efforts to freely share research strategies, methodologies, and data with related SwafS projects; where appropriate, describe the implementation of open science practices notably citizen engagement component – half a page]

PROJECT IDENTITY

PROJECT NAME	Give the full name followed by the acronym in parentheses. _____
COORDINATOR	Indicate the name, institution, city, country and e-mail address. _____
CONSORTIUM	List all participating entities (institutions). Order the institutions alphabetically, on the first line, followed by the academic unit on the next line. Below that, place the city and the country. Example: Hellenic Foundation for European and Foreign Policy – ELIAMEP – Athens, Greece _____
FUNDING SCHEME	Horizon 2020: SwafS-31-2020 Bottom-up approach to build SwafS knowledge base _____
DURATION	List the dates (month and year) when a project began and will be ended, then the total number of months of its duration (in parentheses). Example: September 2014 – August 2017 (36 months).

BUDGET	<hr/> <p>Indicate the EU budget contribution.</p> <p>Example: EU contribution: 1 000 000 €.</p>
WEBSITE	<hr/> <p>Give the URL of the project website.</p>
FOR MORE INFORMATION	<hr/> <p>Provide the names and e-mail addresses of one or two project participants who have agreed to serve as general contact persons. Place the word "Contact" in front of the first full name.</p>
FURTHER READING	<hr/> <p>List up to five current or forthcoming publications the project has produced that might be of interest to policymakers.</p>

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ANNEX VI PROJECT INFORMATION SHEET

Critical Making: Studying RRI Principles in the Maker Community

The Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic has shown the importance of the global maker community for a rapid response to the lack of medical hardware supplies and reveals the great social innovation potential of the maker movement.

In **Critical Making** we add scientific insights into the potentials of the maker movement for critical, socially responsible making, and show how these communities can offer new opportunities for young makers of all genders to contribute to an open society via open innovation. We study grassroots innovation processes taking place in maker spaces, hacker spaces, fablabs, etc. and online spaces and relate them to RRI practices. More specifically, we search for and analyse existing innovation and co-design processes taking place in these open spaces to find out in how far they reflect or contradict RRI principles.

Following a mixed method approach enables us to collect data, analyse it, actively improve practices and develop theories and synthesise findings. Next to analysing existing practices, we co-design, evaluate and disseminate concrete interventions that aim to foster RRI principles in the maker movement. In three case actions the project specifically looks at aspects of gender, openness and the recruitment of young talents. As a result, we will co-define measure how to better implement RRI principles in the open innovation movement taking place across maker communities. Our findings will provide hands-on input for practitioners in the field and will enrich the scientific knowledge base in the RRI community on innovation processes outside of academia, aiming to harness the full innovation potential of the global grassroots maker movement.

Type of intervention

The purpose of the (type of project activity: e.g. workshop (1) / focus group discussion (2) / interview (3) / questionnaire (4)) is to better understand the (reason of project activity: e.g. main barriers, enablers, supporting conditions, motivation, etc.)

Selection of participants

The **Critical Making** project aims to include as many participants in the citizen science projects as possible. Participation is hence not limited to specific groups. The citizen science projects have also made efforts to provide their data in different forms to allow for example the visually impaired, the elderly and children to take part in science activities.

Voluntary participation

Please be aware that your participation is completely voluntary. You may refuse to participate or withdraw your participation at any time without providing any reasons. Your participation in **Critical Making** is highly valued and will definitely make a significant contribution in frontier physics. Without the participation of a considerable number of citizen scientists, this study will be compromised.

Procedure

The procedure for your participation will be as follows:

Workshop(s) (1)

You will take part in the following workshop (describe the type of the workshop). The workshop will be moderated and guided by (name of the workshop's moderator). The whole workshop will be documented by (give the name of the documenting person) and the documentation material will be shared (please indicate, where the workshop materials are documented). Personal information about you will not be shared on the website or other related platforms unless you explicitly agreed in advance.

Focus group discussion (2)

You will take part in a discussion with other citizen scientists from the local community or region. This discussion will be guided by (provide the name of the moderator). The discussion will take place in (name the location of the focus group discussion), and no one else but the people who take part in the discussion and the moderator will be present during this discussion. The entire discussion might be tape-recorded for further analysis, but no-one will be identified by name on the data-material. The tape will be kept (explain, how the tape will be stored). The information recorded will be handled confidentially, and no one else except (name of person(s) with access to the tapes) will be allowed to listen to the tapes. The tapes will be destroyed after (indicate the period of time).

Interview (3)

You will participate in an interview with (name of the interviewer). If you do not wish to answer any of the questions during the interview, you may refuse to answer and we will move on to the next question. The information tape-recorded will be handled confidentially, and no one else except (name of person(s) with access to the information) will have access to the information gathered during the interview. (The tapes will be destroyed after a period of time).

Questionnaire (4)

You will fill out a questionnaire which will be provided by (name of distributor of blank questionnaire) and collected by (name of collector of completed questionnaires). The information recorded will be handled confidentially, and no one else except (name of person(s) with access to the information) will have access to the completed questionnaire. The results of the questionnaire will be reported only in aggregated form.

Benefits

We expect a direct benefit for you in that, you will (explain, what are the benefits for the participants). Additionally, other citizen scientists involved in the **Critical Making** activities may benefit from your contribution in the following ways: (explain, why other citizen scientists could also benefit from the participant's contribution.)

Reimbursements

You will not be provided with any payment to take part in the project activities. Material for the (select the type of intervention: workshops/focus group discussions/interviews/questionnaires) will be provided by the project. Refreshments during the course of these activities will be provided by the project.

Confidentiality

Your individual-related information will not be shared with anyone outside the **Critical Making** project team directly involved in the different activities that you will participate in and only for the purposes of the Project. This data will be stored securely by the involved project team for the duration specified under each activity. Non-personal data extracted from the different activities you will be involved in will be shared with the **Critical Making** evaluation form in an anonymous manner and stored in secure servers on the project portal. Any research results resulting from the analysis of your data and that of other citizen scientists involved will be presented in an aggregated form and cannot be traced back to you.

(The following text applies for focus group discussions):

We will ask you and others in the group not to talk to people outside the group about what was said within the group. We will, in other words, ask each participant to keep what was said in the group confidential.

Sharing of research findings

We will be sharing what we have learnt from the different activities that you will be involved in with other **Critical Making** participants and with the community. We will do this by providing a written report which will not include your personal data. Rather, the findings will be reported in a general and aggregated form to ensure that you personally cannot be identified. Nothing that you will tell us today will be shared with anybody outside the research team and nothing will be attributed to you by name. We might also publish the results in academic publications in order to widen the scope of our research. Data will only be included in these publications in aggregated and anonymised form.

Right to refuse or withdraw

You may choose to opt-out or withdraw your participation at any time.

Who to Contact

If you have any questions you may ask them now or later, even after the participation. If you wish to ask questions later, you may contact any of the following team members: (name, address/telephone number/e-mail of contact person).

This project has been reviewed and approved by the European Union's research and innovation programme Horizon 2020 (Grant Agreement no. 101006285), including an ethical screening to make sure that participants are protected from harm and their privacy is respected at all times.

ANNEX VII INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPANTS

Certificate of Consent

Statement by the participant giving consent:

I have read the foregoing information, or the information has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions that I have asked, have been answered to my satisfaction.

I hereby give consent for my data to be documented and used for the purposes of the **Critical Making** project as stated in the project information sheet. I confirm that I have been informed of the nature of **Critical Making** and that my participation is voluntary. I am aware that I may withdraw my consent at any time.

Print name of participant:

Signature of participant:

Date (day/month/year):

Statement by the project team member receiving consent:

I have provided the project information sheet to the participant for their perusal or/and I have accurately read out the information sheet to the participant, and to the best of my ability made sure that the person understands the process.

I confirm that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by him/her have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

Print name of project team member/person taking the consent

.....

Signature of project team member/person taking the consent

Date (day/month/year):

ANNEX VIII INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPANTS

Certificate of Consent for parent(s)/guardian(s)

Statement by the parent/guardian giving consent:

I have been asked to give consent for my daughter/son to participate in this research study of the **Critical Making** project, which will involve her/him in the following project activities:

- Workshop(s)
- Focus group discussion
- Interview
- Questionnaire(s)

I have read the project information sheet or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions that I have asked, have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily for my child to participate in the above activities for this study.

Print name of parent/guardian:

Print name of child:

A certificate of assent will be completed (yes/no)

Signature of parent/guardian:

Date (day/month/year):

Statement by the project team member receiving consent:

I have provided the project information sheet or/and I have accurately read out the information sheet to the parent/guardian, and to the best of my ability made sure that the person understands the process.

I confirm that the parent/guardian was given an opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by him/her have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

Print name of project team member/person taking the consent

Signature of project team member/person taking the consent

Date (day/month/year):

ANNEX IX CERTIFICATE OF ASSENT (CHILDREN)

Certificate of Assent

The **Critical Making** project is studying how makerspaces, which are new types of workshops, with tools such as 3D printers or laser cutters, are engaging people and act in a responsible way. For example, we want to find out how young people can engage in making activities and learn how to create innovative solutions for the benefits of society and the environment.

I understand my involvement in the Critical Making project.

I have read the project information (or had the information read to me). I have had my questions answered and know that I can also ask questions later if I have them.

I agree to take part in the research.

Print name of child:

Signature/initials of child:

Date (day/month/year):

Statement by the project team member receiving assent:

I have accurately read out the information sheet to the potential participant, and to the best of my ability made sure, that the child understands the process she/he will be involved in within the framework of the Critical Making project.

I confirm that the child was given an opportunity to ask questions about the project, and all the questions asked by her/him have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm, that the child has not been coerced into giving assent, and the assent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this assent form has been provided to the participant and their parent/guardian.

Print name of project team member/person taking the assent

Signature of project team member/person taking the assent

Date (day/month/year):

Parent(s)/guardian(s) has/have signed the certificate of consent: YES / NO

(initialed by researcher/assistant)

ANNEX X DATA EXCHANGE FORM

As research partners in the **Critical Making** consortium, we agree to share personal identifiable information (PII) of individuals and/or organisations as defined in the confidentiality agreement of the project.

This data exchange form documents the exchange between partners regarding sensitive data:

Researcher(s) responsible for the data (who collected the data originally)	
Type of data (e.g. interview recording, questionnaires, etc.)	
Sensitivity of data (describe briefly why this specific data is highly sensible e.g. personal data of participants)	
Consent form signed by all involved participants	
Storage location	
Person(s) who have access to the data	
Purpose of sharing	
Confidentiality agreement signed?	
Data retention (timeframe for storing the shared data)	

Date:

Name & organisation:

Signature: